

Nanopore long-read sequencing of circRNAs

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ABSTRACT

Circular RNA (circRNA) is a group of highly stable RNA molecules with suggested roles in development and disease. They derive from linear pre-mRNAs when a 5'-splice site splices back to an upstream 3'-splice site in a process termed back-splicing. Most circRNAs are multi-exonic and may contain several thousand nucleotides. The extensive sequence overlap between the linear and circular forms of an RNA means that circRNA identification depends on the detection of back-splice-junction sequence reads that are unique to the circRNA. However, the short-read length obtained using standard next-generation sequencing techniques means that the internal sequence, exon composition and alternative splicing of circRNAs are unknown in many cases. Recently, several labs, including ours, have reported protocols for sequencing of circRNAs using long-read nanopore sequencing and thereby expanded our understanding of circRNA size distribution and internal splicing patterns. Here, we review these protocols and discuss the different approaches taken to study the full length composition of circRNAs.

1. Introduction

CircRNAs are a group of RNAs defined by a covalent bond between the 5' and 3' end formed by a process known as back-splicing. The existence of these peculiar RNAs has been known since the seventies [1,2] but it is only within the last decade that it has become recognized that circRNAs are expressed in a cell type- and development-specific manner and are thought to function in a range of different biological processes [3–9]. The exons that undergo back-splicing often reside in known genes, making it difficult to distinguish sequence reads from the circRNA and linear RNA using short-read sequencing platforms such as Illumina (Fig. 1A–C). CircRNA mapping depends solely on reads that span the circRNA-specific back-splice-junction (BSJ), which means that the internal composition of exons in circRNAs (>100–150 nucleotides away from the BSJ) is often unknown (Fig. 1C). Since >14% of circRNAs in human and >10% in mouse are >800 nucleotides (nt) in length, according to the circAtlas database, and consist of several exons, full characterization by short-read sequencing is not feasible [10]. Hence, it is difficult to conclude whether alternatively spliced exons found in short-read sequencing data derive from linear or circRNAs.

Long-read sequencing techniques, recently developed by companies

such as Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) or Pacific Biosciences (PacBio), produce sequencing reads of several thousand nt and therefore provide full coverage of the internal exon composition of linear RNA [11–15] (Fig. 1D); however, until recently those methods were not compatible with circRNA sequencing protocols (Fig. 1E).

As illustrated in Fig. 1, circRNA and linear RNA sequences can only be differentiated by reads that contain the BSJ. This means that short-read sequencing technologies are limited to the BSJ region, while long-read sequencing can reveal the full structure of a circRNA in a single read. However, as we discuss in this review, the library preparation process for long-read sequencing poses a challenge for circRNAs given their lack of free 3' ends. In addition, ONT sequencing tends to have a higher error-rate compared to short-read sequencing and is more expensive. On the positive side, ONT sequencing can be done in a more portable setup that will be feasible in any lab.

2. Challenges for long-read sequencing of circRNAs

The main challenge for circRNA sequencing is that total RNA isolated from a cell or tissue of interest mostly encompasses linear RNA (>97% rRNA and tRNA and 2–3% mRNA) whereas circRNAs generally

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constitute <0.01% of the total RNA pool. The minute amount of circRNA becomes particularly critical for long-read sequencing, which currently provides <10% of the sequence depth obtained by short-read sequencing at the same cost. This means that pre-purification and amplification of circRNA species become necessary steps but this may introduce biases in the final sequencing library. Another challenge is that circRNAs by definition lack a 3' terminal poly(A) sequence, which is required for library construction aimed for long-read sequencing [11–13]. Furthermore, the relatively high error rate seen for nanopore sequencing (usually 4–6% for the standard setup) calls for special bioinformatic methods to identify circRNAs. Recently, three papers have described four methods for nanopore-dependent long-read sequencing of circRNAs [16–18]. Here, we review the key features in each method and discuss advantages and disadvantages.

3. Available approaches for circRNA Long-Read sequencing

3.1. CircRNA nicking and long-read sequencing (CircNick-LRS)

We initially developed circNick-LRS as a technique for global circRNA profiling by long-read sequencing and posted it on bioRxiv in 2019 [19]. An extended version of the technique was recently published along with an alternative method, circPanel-LRS, for analysing a set of specific circRNAs [16].

To enrich for circRNAs, circNick-LRS uses a modified version of the RPAD protocol [20]. Briefly, following rRNA depletion, RNase R treatment is used to digest linear RNA. Any undigested linear RNAs are then polyadenylated and removed via binding to oligo-dT beads (Fig. 2A-B). The enriched circRNA pool is linearized using an optimized gentle

Fig. 1. Revealing full-length structure of linear RNA and circRNAs using long-read sequencing. A) Primary RNA transcript containing six exons and five introns. B) A pre-mRNA undergoing linear canonical alternative splicing and producing different polyadenylated linear RNA isoforms. C) Alternative splicing of the pre-mRNA into different circRNA isoforms. The first and last exons of the pre-mRNA cannot be included in the circRNA due to the nature of the back-splicing process. Some circRNA isoforms contain exons or retained introns that are not found in the linear mRNA. Short-read sequencing only detects the circRNAs based on reads mapped to the BSJ. The origin of short-reads lacking the BSJ sequence cannot be unambiguously assigned to the linear or circular RNA. For example, exon 4, which is only expressed in circRNA cannot be assigned properly. D-E) Long-read sequencing can cover the full length of the linear RNA (D) and the circRNA (E) originating from the same primary RNA transcript. In order to map the full length of the circRNA, the long-read should contain the BSJ.

Fig. 2. Overview of current protocols for circRNA long-read sequencing: A-B) Enrichment of circRNA prior to global sequencing. C) CircPanel-LRS uses circRNA-specific primers (CSP) for cDNA synthesis and an adjacent outward pointing primer for second strand cDNA synthesis. CSP primers are modified at the 5' end to be compatible with ONT-cPRM-adaptor primers for library amplification and nanopore long-read sequencing. D) CircNick-LRS uses gentle hydrolysis to nick the circRNA, followed by polyadenylation. The poly(A) RNA is then amplified by PCR and sequenced following the standard nanopore protocol, but with an added size-selection step that removes PCR products <350 nt (corresponding to circRNA <200 nt). E) The isoCirc initiates cDNA synthesis using random primers. Single-stranded and strand-displaced cDNA overhangs are then digested using Mung Bean nuclease before the cDNA fragments are ligated to form a circular hybrid of circRNA and circular complement cDNA. This cDNA pool is subjected to rolling circle amplification followed by nanopore sequencing. F) CIRI-long uses a modified version of random primers for cDNA synthesis that carry a primer target at the 5' end. Once cDNA synthesis stops due to random template switching, the template switch oligo has a primer target at the 5' end. The obtained cDNA pool is subsequently amplified, size selected for 400 nt, 600 nt and 1 kb and subjected to the nanopore sequencing.

hydrolysis protocol before being polyadenylated and used as input for the Nanopore cDNA-PCR protocol (SQK-PCS109 Nanopore cDNA-PCR sequencing kit) [19] (Fig. 1D).

In parallel, we created long-read datasets for linear poly(A) RNA from the same samples used for circNick-LRS, enabling a direct comparison that allowed us to eliminate potential methodological differences and confirm circRNA-specific splicing events. For this, the cDNA-PCR sequencing kit from Oxford nanopore (SQK-PCS109) was used and library preparation followed by sequencing according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, total RNA was used without rRNA depletion and cDNA synthesis was initiated from oligo-dT primers. After full-length cDNA synthesis followed by template switching, PCR amplification was subsequently performed to enrich the library for long-read nanopore sequencing.

CircRNAs are identified by the presence of BSJ-containing sequence reads and in our study this was seen for 4.4% and 6.2% of the long-reads generated from human and mouse brain samples. This resulted in detection of 18,266 and 39,623 unique circRNAs in human and mouse brain, respectively, of which 2,851 and 11,380 were categorized as novel circRNAs (not annotated in any of the circBase [21], circAtlas [10] or CIRCpedia [22] databases). In total, 5,537 circRNAs were found to be conserved between human and mouse brain. The average size of the full-length detected circRNAs for circNick-LRS was 795 nt in human and 620 nt in mouse.

Our data show that alternative splicing is abundant in circRNAs, with 559 and 681 circRNA isoforms found to contain alternatively spliced exons (covered by ≥ 10 reads) in human and mouse brain samples, respectively. These exons were partially included, giving rise to different circRNA isoforms. Furthermore, 8.5% and 12.4% of the highly expressed exons in human and mouse detected by circNick-LRS (covered by >5 reads) were annotated as novel exons. By applying a very stringent cut-off rate (>20 reads), circNick-LRS found 213 and 384 circRNAs to show full or partial intron-retention in human and mouse brain, respectively. We also noticed that short introns and exons are more likely to be retained in circRNAs. Interestingly, we noticed that many of the novel exons that are preferentially found in circRNAs were microexons (3–29 nt) and that many of them resulted in frame-shifting or the insertion of a stop codon [16,23–24].

We hypothesize that the high proportion of frame-shift- and stop codon-inducing exons in circRNAs may reflect that circRNAs are not subject to nonsense-mediated decay (NMD) in line with the general notion that circRNAs do not undergo translation [25]. Rather, NMD targets translated mRNAs containing a premature termination codon [26] and the pathway is known to be related to some developmental disorders [27,28].

A note of caution for the circNick-LRS method is that depletion of linear polyadenylated RNA via oligo-dT beads may remove circRNAs with short, internal poly(A) stretches [16]. This can cause some biases that affect the ability to compare samples prepared using different enrichment methods. Also, the hydrolysis step used in circNick-LRS may create a bias for longer circRNA since shorter circRNA are less likely to be nicked. Additionally, a size-selection step in the library preparation for circNick-LRS removes circRNAs shorter than 200 nt. This step was included since an abundance of short library fragments reduces the overall quality of the ONT data and means that long library fragments (corresponding to intact circRNAs) will have a lower chance to be sequenced. However, with further development of the ONT kits, this step may be removed from the circNick-LRS protocol in the future.

3.2. CircRNA panel long-read sequencing (CircPanel-LRS)

In conjunction with the global circNick-LRS protocol described above, we also developed a method termed circPanel-LRS to sequence a pre-selected panel of circRNAs at much higher depth [16]. This method allows the simultaneous detection of multiple circRNA isoforms generated from the targeted gene loci and is highly efficient for samples with

very low amount of input material. In this approach, a pool of circRNA-specific primers are used to enrich a specific subset of circRNAs by cDNA synthesis and PCR to amplify and index the samples prior to ONT sequencing (Fig. 2C). The inclusion of a PCR step means that as little as 100 ng total RNA can be used as input without the need for circRNA enrichment. We are currently testing further optimisation of the protocol using 10 ng total RNA as input.

We applied circPanel-LRS for 10 circRNA-producing gene loci and found that 63% and 75% of the long-reads obtained from human brain and SH-SY5Y cells could pass the stringent criteria to be considered BSJ-containing reads [16]. On average, circPanel-LRS detected >35 circRNA isoforms per circRNA gene locus of which 12 were not previously reported. Some of these circRNA isoforms share a BSJ, but their internal exon composition differs (Fig. 3A-B). CircPanel-LRS was also able to generate concatemeric reads resulting from multiple rounds of cDNA synthesis across the same circRNA template. Compared to circNick-LRS, circPanel-LRS detected a higher number of alternatively used and novel exons, most likely due to the increased sequencing depth. Libraries prepared by circPanel-LRS can be sequenced using Flongle, the mini version flowcell designed by Oxford nanopore, which significantly reduces sequencing costs. The main limiting factor for this approach is that only a preselected panel of circRNAs is targeted.

3.3. isoCirc

The isoCirc approach, developed by Xin et al. [17], is a long-read sequencing protocol for global analysis of all circRNAs in a sample of interest. Here, circRNAs are first enriched by rRNA depletion and RNase R treatment. The isoCirc protocol then uses random hexamer primers for cDNA synthesis and relies on the strand displacement activity of the reverse transcriptase to generate cDNAs corresponding to the full circRNA. All single-stranded and strand-displaced cDNAs are digested by Mung Bean nuclease, leaving only the cDNA-RNA hybrids intact. Following a ligation step using SplintR ligase to create a circular cDNA-circRNA hybrid, rolling circle amplification is used to amplify the cDNA by generating long concatemeric ssDNAs that can be used for ONT long-read sequencing (Fig. 2E). The strategy to sequence each circRNA as a multi-copy concatemer is intended to minimize the error rate in Nanopore sequencing by generating a final consensus read.

However, there is a risk that mis-annealed bases from the annealed random hexamer primers can be incorporated, meaning that isoCirc may introduce additional errors in the circularized cDNA sequence, in particular if the RT enzyme used shows inefficient strand displacement activity. This would result in a systematic and clustered errors detected as indels (insertion/deletions) in the concatemers and the final consensus read.

Xin et al. sequenced circRNAs from HEK293 cells and twelve different human tissues, leading to the detection of 107,147 full-length circRNA isoforms across all sequenced samples of which 40,628 circRNA isoforms were ≥ 500 nt in length. They also found that a significant number of splicing events occur in circRNAs.

The average length for BSJ-containing consensus sequences in isoCirc is between 300 and 460 nt, suggesting that the study mainly captures smaller circRNAs than seen with circNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS. A possible explanation for this is the high concentration of random hexamer primers (100 pmol) used for cDNA synthesis in isoCirc as this may partially block elongation of the RT enzyme. Furthermore, the preference for amplifying and covering the BSJ of shorter circRNA by rolling circle amplification may lead to overrepresentation of shorter circRNA.

According to the numbers provided by Xin et al. isoCirc generates about 1 read per circRNA isoform per tissue for most of the detected circRNA isoforms, which may limit the ability to differentiate circRNAs produced from loci with multiple isoforms. In comparison to circNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS, isoCirc reports a higher percentage of novel circRNA isoforms (53.1% of the high-confidence BSJs covered with ≥ 2

Fig. 3. Examples of circPanel-LRS output obtained from human brain total RNA sample. Overview of the circRNA isoforms detected with >10 reads from the RMST (A) and RIMS1 (B) gene loci, respectively. The targeted exons are indicated by the red arrow.

reads found in one of the HEK293 biological replicates). This difference may be explained by the different reference databases used by Xin et al. (circBase and MiOncoCirc) [29] and Rahimi et al. (circBase, circAtlas and CIRCpedia).

3.4. CIRI-long

Zhang et al. introduced another method named CIRI-long to perform long-read nanopore sequencing of circRNAs [18]. CIRI-long enriches for circRNAs by rRNA depletion followed by RNase R treatment of the polyadenylated or non-polyadenylated RNA and resembles isoCirc in initiating cDNA synthesis using random hexamer primers (Fig. 2F). However, the second strand synthesis relies on random template switching to add primer targets at the 3' end of the first strand of cDNA. To accomplish this, Zhang et al. replaced the T(30)N-1 N-3' sequence

with random hexamers in the VNP primer taken from SMARTer cDNA synthesis kit (Takara Bio). This modified oligo and the template switch sequence located at the 5' and 3' ends of the generated cDNA, respectively, facilitate second strand synthesis of the cDNA and PCR amplification for nanopore sequencing. In addition, CIRI-long applies a library size selection step of 400 nt, 600 nt and 1 kb lengths before long-read sequencing.

Zhang et al. performed circRNA enrichment and nanopore long-read sequencing of mouse brain samples and detected 115,755 alternative circularization events from 15,905 genes. This was significantly more than what was detected using short-read sequencing in a similar setup. In total, Zhang et al. found 90,759 circRNA exons and 6,714 alternative splicing events in their nanopore generated BSJ-containing reads. They also reported 156 circRNAs derived from the mitochondrial genome.

We noticed that the average length of the raw reads given in the CIRI-

long approach indicates low efficiency in generating concatemers for the individual circRNA. In addition, and according to the circRNA concatemers presented in the paper and supplemental data, CIRI-long mainly covers smaller circRNAs with an average size of 300 nt. The total length distribution of the circRNAs detected by CIRI-long has an average size of <500 nt and the median size of about 600 nt length distribution is reported for the circRNAs supported by more than two long reads.

4. Comparing the methods

Overall, we find that all four methods described in this review complement each other and benefit the circRNA community. CircNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS capture a larger size-range of full-length circRNAs and yield a higher coverage of alternative splicing events at the sequencing depth applied. CircPanel-LRS output depends on the targeted exon and almost captures all circRNA isoforms originating from the same gene locus and sharing the targeted exon (Fig. 3A-B). The nicking step in circNick-LRS may result in more than one cut in some circRNAs but to minimize the problem, three different nicking conditions were optimized to three aliquots of each enriched circRNA pool to favor single-hit kinetics for all sizes of circRNA [16]. Even under these conditions the nicking step could favour detection of larger circRNAs, which are more likely to be cut than smaller circRNA, and this may contribute to the larger average size circRNA observed using this method. A more detailed bioinformatic analysis is required to fully elucidate potential biases using the different approaches. However, full-length sequencing of small circRNAs is possible using short-read sequencing technology and with significantly lower costs compared to long-read sequencing.

A generic problem about analysing circRNAs on a relatively low sequencing depth platform like ONT is the requirement for larger amounts of input RNA. The methods described here address this differently. Both circNick-LRS and isoCirc use relatively large amounts of RNA (20 µg). In contrast, the CIRI-long protocol only uses 1 µg total RNA to make sequencing libraries, which means that less than a few nanograms will be available after the purification steps described in the study. However, all the methods use PCR amplification to generate enough library for sequencing on the nanopore platform.

In the CIRI-long paper by Zhang et al., the PCR steps required to get enough material for nanopore sequencing were not mentioned; however, in a recent correction, the authors have now included PCR steps in the methods section. In our view, it remains unclear how this PCR step is compatible with the authors' conclusion that their method involves direct sequencing of the cDNA derived from circRNA.

A notable difference between the methods discussed above is the size differences of the mapped circRNAs. This may be explained by several of the arbitrary conditions applied in each method. CircNick-LRS performs a size cut-off in the library construction that eliminates circRNAs below 200 nt and the nicking step may bias the method towards inclusion of larger circRNA. In contrast, the use of random hexamer primers for the RT step in both isoCirc and CIRI-long (especially when used in a high molar ratio) tends to generate short cDNAs, particularly when combined with an RT enzyme with weak strand displacement and RNase H activity such as the SMARTScribe used by CIRI-long. The RNase H domain of the RT enzyme will partly digest the RNA behind the cDNA synthesis process from the RNA-cDNA hybrid and this makes it difficult to generate long cDNA concatemers from the same circRNA template.

One of the important factors during circRNA long-read nanopore sequencing is preparing the full-length circRNA library and adjusting these libraries to add the sequencing adaptors and barcodes required for long-read sequencing. CircNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS adjust and follow the manufacturer's (ONT) library preparation steps for cDNA-PCR and cDNA-PCR barcoding, which reduces potential PCR biases. The isoCirc approach uses different library preparation kits and the ONT ligation sequencing kit to add ONT-sequencing adaptors to the rolling circle

amplified libraries. CIRI-long combines reagents from different manufacturers to first amplify the libraries by PCR and then uses nanopore ligation and barcode expansion kits to ligate barcodes and sequencing adaptors to the library. This approach may cause some biases, since Oxford Nanopore has warned that ligating barcodes of the type used for CIRI-long should be avoided for PCR amplicon sequencing since a significant portion of the reads would come from artificial concatemers (5–7% for 1 kb size amplicons).

One of the most crucial steps in mapping circRNA based on long-read sequencing is mapping the data to the corresponding reference genome and transcriptome. To reliably confirm the circRNA specificity of a detected splicing event and differentiate it from its linear counterpart, it is highly recommended to sequence the full-length poly(A) linear RNA from the same sample as described for circNick-LRS approach [16].

We conclude that all methods introduce intrinsic biases and that one may want to combine the methods for more comprehensive coverage of the circRNA landscape. Also, more stringent quantification of specific circRNAs may require validation by RT-qPCR or Northern blot with strategically placed primers or probes.

5. Comparison of the bioinformatics methods

The four methods, (CIRI-long, isoCirc, circNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS) all tackle the complicated problem of distinguishing the internal structure of circRNAs from the structure of linear transcripts from the same host gene. While they all rely on Nanopore long-read sequencing, the approaches have substantial differences in the algorithms used to achieve this, mainly between the use of rolling circle amplification (CIRI-long, isoCirc) or not (circNick-LRS, circPanel-LRS). The CIRI-long algorithm, which is part of the CIRI suite of circRNA-centered analysis tools, splits the concatemeric reads produced by rolling circle amplification into repetitive fragments. This is done by searching for identical repeated nucleotide sequences (called k-mers) to detect the boundaries of circRNAs. The repeated read fragments are then aligned to generate a consensus sequence, which is aligned to the genome.

The isoCirc algorithm also detects repetitive fragments in the rolling circle generated reads, but little information is given about how this is done. The most likely approach is by use of the Tandem Repeats Finder algorithm (<https://github.com/Benson-Genomics-Lab/TRF>) [30].

A vulnerability when generating consensus circRNA sequences based on tandem repeats is the risk that circRNAs with naturally occurring repeated sequences could be collapsed resulting in partial circRNA sequences identified.

For genome mapping, CIRI-long uses minimap2 and bwa mappers, whereas isoCirc only uses minimap2 and the long-read circRNA algorithm behind circNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS uses pBLAT. All algorithms use splice sites from known exon annotations and canonical de novo GT/AG splice signals to align junction sites. Furthermore, CIRI-long scans for non-canonical splice signals if canonical signals are not present. For isoCirc, circNick-LRS, and circPanel-LRS only canonical splice sites are used per default but non-canonical signals can also be investigated.

While the algorithms behind CIRI-long and isoCirc are produced specifically for their respective implementation of rolling circle amplification, the long-read circRNA detection algorithm behind circNick-LRS, circPanel-LRS is a general-purpose approach applicable to long-read circRNA enriched sequencing, exemplified by the same bioinformatics approach being used for both circNick-LRS, circPanel-LRS (Table 1).

6. Conclusion

The use of long-read sequencing methods to analyse full length circRNA sequences will help to elucidate the function of circRNAs. It has enabled the distinction of the exon composition of circRNAs at unprecedented detail and revealed a large number of splicing events that

Table 1
Comparison of key algorithmic aspects.

Methods	Sequencing approach	Repeat processing	Mapping	CircRNA detection principle
CIRI-long	CircRNA enriched, rolling circle amplified, Nanopore sequencing	Consensus sequences generated from RCA tandem repeats	Minimap2 and BWA	Annotated exons, de novo GT/AG and non-consensus splice signals
isoCirc	CircRNA enriched, rolling circle amplified, Nanopore sequencing	Consensus sequences generated from RCA tandem repeats	Minimap2	Annotated exons, de novo GT/AG
CircNick-LRS	CircRNA enriched and nicked, polyadenylated and cDNA amplified, Nanopore sequencing	No repeat processing	pBLAT	Annotated exons, de novo GT/AG
CircPanel-LRS	Total RNA used for cDNA-PCR amplification, Nanopore sequencing	No repeat processing	pBLAT	Annotated exons, de novo GT/AG

are preferentially or exclusively seen in circRNAs compared to mRNAs. In particular, the four methods mentioned here found many new examples of intron retention, novel exon usage and microexons. Some of the latter have been reported to be associated with neuronal dysfunction and play a function in diseases, but based on a presumed inclusion in linear mRNA [23,24,31]. This raises the possibility that some microexons may exert their function within a circRNA rather than in a protein-coding mRNA. We predict that long-read sequencing of circRNA from different tissues, developmental stages and pathogenic conditions will provide a much deeper understanding of circRNA functions and role in disease in the future.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors developed and reported the use of circNick-LRS and circPanel-LRS methods.

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